

Exploring Learners' Attitude towards Peer Group Study Across Different Levels of Education in West Bengal

Paper Id : 19876 Submission Date : 2025-01-03 Acceptance Date : 2025-01-21 Publication Date : 2025-01-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15150032

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Abstract

Peer group study helps in better understanding and learning of a concept and enhances students' teamwork skills. The main objective of this study is to explore the attitude of learners based on their locality and gender towards peer group study across different levels of education. In this study, a total of 624 samples were selected from various schools, colleges and universities in West Bengal through Stratified random sampling technique. The researcher used a self-made questionnaire for data collection. It was a descriptive survey method. 'Mean', 'Standard Deviation' and 't-test' were used for data analysis. The study found that learners' attitude towards peer group study across different levels of education in West Bengal is overall positive.

Keywords Learners' attitude, Peer group study, different levels of education.

Introduction

A student's behaviour changes through learning. A variety of experiences help students change this pattern of behaviour. Learners use a variety of strategies to learn any content. One of these methods is peer group study. The main objective of this research work is to know the attitude of learners towards peer group study. If students' attitude towards peer group study is known, it will be possible to make students aware of cooperative learning, group work skills etc. Students will also be aware of solving problems in divergent way from this study. Apart from these, studying with a group of friends gives an opportunity to create "we feeling" attitude and it increases knowledge sharing ability. This study can also play a crucial role in creating the mindset of students to help others. In this sense, peer group study becomes important.

Peer group study: Peer group study is a type of collaborative learning method where students study together with each other in a small group with their friends according to a specific and common goal. It is a type of method where different students teach each other. A student can teach a concept well to another student only when the student himself fully knows and understands that particular concept. So, it can be said that, this is a kind of collaborative, interdependent, shared and participatory learning method that students perform in a group with their friends to strengthen their knowledge.

Statement of the problem: Exploring learners' attitude towards peer group study across different levels of education in West Bengal.

Objective of study

1. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female secondary students in West Bengal.
2. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female undergraduate students in West Bengal.
3. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female post-graduate students in West Bengal.
4. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban secondary students in West Bengal.
5. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban undergraduate students in West Bengal.
6. To find out the difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban post-graduate students in West Bengal

Review of Literature

Aliyu & Fareo (2024), worked on "Influence of peer group on attitude towards education among senior secondary school students in Numan education zone, Adamawa state, Nigeria". The researchers found that, there is a significant difference in mean responses of male and female senior secondary students on the peer group activities. Motivation, mutual support, shared learning experiences can create positive peer interaction. This study also found that peer group interaction can change students' attitudes toward education.

Mntuyedwa (2023), conducted a study on "Exploring the benefits of joining peer groups for first-year students: A case study of a South African university". This study revealed that, if students join peer groups, their outcomes improve and their leadership skills and willingness to participate in co-curricular activities also increase.

Ebrahim et al. (2023), studied on "Students' Perception of Peer Learning: A Study in a Private Malaysian Medical School". The result indicated that there is a significant difference in perception of peer learning among medical students from different study years. Students are aware of peer learning and they are willing and eager to participate in peer group discussions and this enhances their academic performance.

Reang & Kaipeng (2022), conducted "A Study on the Influence of Peer Group on Academic Performance of Students". This study found that peer group slightly influences learners' outcomes and academic achievement.

Furo & Kagu (2020), studied on "Peer Group Influence on Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students in Faculty of Education, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria". This study found that peers' group interactions positively influence students' academic achievement and lead to behavioural changes.

Abdulrahman (2020), worked on "INFLUENCE OF PEER GROUP ON ADOLESCENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ILORIN METROPOLIS, KWARA STATE". This study suggested that, peer groups positively influence the academic achievement of adolescent students.

Liu & Chen (2020), in their study entitled "Effects of peer learning on learning performance, motivation, and attitude" found that students in the peer learning group had higher final exam marks and semester grades than the lecture-based group. It was also found that the learning motivation score of the peer learning group was significantly higher than the lecture-based group in the post-test and the peer learning group showed more positive attitude towards peer learning than the lecture-based group.

Basit Olalekan (2016) conducted a study on "Influence of peer group relationship on the academic performance of students in secondary schools (a case study of selected secondary schools in Atiba local government area of Oyo state)". The results indicated that peer group affects learning as well as socioeconomic status and students are more interested in peer group than teachers and parents.

Ikakena (2013), studied on "Parents, teachers and pupils' attitudes towards peer-group influence on pupils' academic performance in selected high schools of Sesheke district, Zambia". This study found that parents and teachers have negative attitudes towards peer group influence on students' academic performance and students have positive attitudes.

To the best of my knowledge, by reviewing multiple studies it appears that no research work has been done so far on the attitude of the secondary, undergraduate and post-graduate students of West Bengal towards Peer group study based on their gender and locality. So, the researcher selected this study.

Methodology The researcher used Descriptive survey method in this study.

Variables: The researcher selected gender and locality as categorical variables and attitude towards peer group study as dependent variable in this study.

Population: All the secondary, undergraduate and post-graduate students of West Bengal are the population of this research work.

Sample: The researcher selected 624 students as sample from West Bengal in this study. Among them, there are 432 secondary students (216 male students, 216 female students and 292 rural students, 140 urban students), 128 undergraduate students (56 male students, 72 female students and 84 rural students, 44 urban students) and there are 64

post-graduate students (28 male students, 36 female students and 24 rural students, 40 urban students). The researcher chose the sample through Stratified random sampling technique.

Tool: The researcher used a self-made questionnaire for data collection in this study. All the items in the questionnaire are kept as multiple-choice questions. Four options are given for each item. These four options are 'Strongly Agree', 'Agree', 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree'. The questionnaire has total 14 items.

Standardization of the Instrument: A pilot study was conducted on 32 students before applying the self-made questionnaire by the researcher. The validity of the questionnaire was checked by the expert. Basically, face validity was judged here. Split half method and Cronbach's alpha were used to judge the reliability of the questionnaire. The value of "Spearman Brown Coefficient" in Split half method was 0.96. On the other hand, the value of "Cronbach's alpha" was 0.89. So, it can be said that the questionnaire used in this research work is completely valid and reliable.

Statistical Procedures: After collecting data from the secondary, undergraduate and post-graduate students, the researcher used two types of statistical methods to analyse and interpret the data, one is descriptive statistics and the other is inferential statistics. The researcher used 'Mean' and 'Standard Deviation' as descriptive statistics and 't-test' as inferential statistics. The significance level was taken as 0.05% and 0.01% level.

Analysis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female secondary students in West Bengal

Table 1: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female secondary students

Category (Gender)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Male	216	43.7037037	5.323505156
Female	216	42.12962963	5.476533605
df	430	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	3.0290	Significant	Significant

Fig 1: Attitude of male and female secondary students

Interpretation: From the above table number 1, it is seen that the computed t-value is 3.0290 which is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is highly significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is rejected at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female secondary students in West Bengal. It also appears that both male and female secondary students have a positive attitude towards peer group study. Male secondary students have higher positive attitude than female secondary students. The mean difference of male and female secondary students on peer group study is graphically represented above.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female undergraduate students in West Bengal

Table2: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female undergraduate students

Category (Gender)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Male	56	41.21428571	8.074008322
Female	72	42.27777778	5.241283098
df	126	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	0.9005	Not Significant	Not Significant

Fig 2: Attitude of male and female undergraduate students

Interpretation: From the above table number 2, it is seen that the computed t-value is 0.9005 which is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is not significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is accepted at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female undergraduate students in West Bengal. It appears that both male and female undergraduate students also have a positive attitude towards peer group study. The mean difference of male and female undergraduate students on peer group study is graphically represented above.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female post-graduate students in West Bengal.

Table3: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of male and female post-graduate students

Category (Gender)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Male	28	43.85714286	5.948633741
Female	36	46.66666667	5.93295879
df	62	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	1.8772	Not Significant	Not Significant

Fig 3: Attitude of male and female post-graduate students

Interpretation: From the above table number 3, it is seen that the computed t-value is 1.8772 which is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is not significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is accepted at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female post-graduate students in West Bengal. The mean values also indicate that male and female post-graduate students have a positive attitude towards peer group study. The mean difference of male and female post-graduate students on peer group study is graphically represented above.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban secondary students in West Bengal

Table 4: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban secondary students

Category (Locality)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Rural	292	43.49315068	5.608347455
Urban	140	41.71428571	4.914061038
df	430	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	3.2083	Significant	Significant

Fig 4: Attitude of rural and urban secondary students

Interpretation: From the above table number 4, it is seen that the computed t-value is 3.2083 which is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is highly significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is rejected at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban secondary students in West Bengal. It also appears that secondary students have

positive attitudes towards peer group study, depending on their locality. Rural secondary students have higher positive attitude than urban secondary students. The mean difference of rural and urban secondary students on peer group study is graphically represented above.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban undergraduate students in West Bengal

Table 5: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban undergraduate students

Category (Locality)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Rural	84	43.23809524	6.239437431
Urban	44	39.09090909	6.547920607
df	126	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	3.5115	Significant	Significant

Fig 5: Attitude of rural and urban undergraduate students

Interpretation: From the above table number 5, it is seen that the computed t-value is 3.5115 which is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is highly significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is rejected at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban undergraduate students in West Bengal. Both undergraduate students have a positive attitude towards peer group study. It also appears that rural undergraduate students have higher positive attitude than urban undergraduate students. The mean difference of rural and urban undergraduate students on peer group study is graphically represented above

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban post-graduate students in West Bengal

Table 6: Difference in attitude towards Peer group study of rural and urban post-graduate students

Category (Locality)	Number (N)	Mean	SD
Rural	24	46.33333333	3.985480896
Urban	40	44.9	7.008419845
df	62	Level of Significance (%)	
		0.05%	0.01%
t-value	0.9152	Not Significant	Not Significant

Fig 6: Attitude of rural and urban post-graduate students

Interpretation: From the above table number 6, it is seen that the computed t-value is 0.9152 which is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05% level and the table value 2.58 at 0.01% level. So here, the null hypothesis is not significant at 0.05% and 0.01% level. It means that null hypothesis is accepted at both levels. So, it can be said that- There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban post-graduate students in West Bengal. The mean values also indicate that rural and urban post-graduate students have a positive attitude towards peer group study. The mean difference of rural and urban post-graduate students on peer group study is graphically represented above.

Findings

1. There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female secondary students in West Bengal. Male secondary students have higher positive attitude than female secondary students.
2. There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female undergraduate students in West Bengal. Both have positive attitudes towards peer group study.
3. There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of male and female post-graduate students in West Bengal. Here too, the attitude of the students is found to be positive.
4. There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban secondary students in West Bengal. Rural secondary students have higher positive attitude than urban secondary students.
5. There is a significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban undergraduate students in West Bengal. Urban undergraduate students have lower positive attitude than rural undergraduate students.
6. There is no significant difference in attitude towards peer group study of rural and urban post-graduate students in West Bengal. Post-graduate students have also been found to have positive attitudes

Conclusion

Peer group study helps to develop teamwork skills, groupwork mentality, and a spirit of cooperation among students. Therefore, it is important to know the attitudes of learners at different levels of education towards peer group study. Because, it can help in taking appropriate measures to make learning effective. The findings of the study show that there is a significant difference in the attitude of secondary students in West Bengal towards peer group study based on their locality and gender. Male secondary students were found to have higher positive attitudes than female secondary students, and students from urban areas were found to have lower positive attitudes than those from rural areas. Therefore, students from urban areas and female secondary students need to be made aware of peer group study. On the other hand, urban undergraduate students were also found to have lower positive attitudes compared to rural undergraduate students. It has also been observed that there is no significant attitudinal difference among post-graduate students based on their locality and gender. Therefore, it is understood that learners' attitude towards peer group study across different levels of education in West Bengal is overall positive. But, the attitude towards peer group study among school and college students in urban areas is less than that of rural area students. Therefore, all these learners need to be made more aware of peer group study. It is necessary to ensure that students are willing to participate in peer group study to make their learning fruitful. They need to increase awareness about how to utilize its benefits so that learners can meet their learning goals. Teachers and parents also need to be aware so that the positive aspects of peer group study can be further improved and

its issues can be resolved. As a result, appropriate decisions can be made in making various administrative decisions or policies for the effective learning of students.

Suggestions for the future Study After completing this study, it is suggested that if any researcher wants to work on this topic in the future, the work can be done with a larger number of samples from states other than West Bengal. It is recommended to include other variables such as streams and socioeconomic status, rather than limiting categorical variables to gender and locality. It is also suggested to use qualitative or mixed methods rather than limiting the study to a quantitative approach. Additionally, other statistics besides the t-test can be used to make the study's findings much stronger. This same research can be conducted separately on a specific subject or on several subjects and compared between them. Finally, it is suggested that, participation in peer group study should ensure that learners' educational needs and goals are properly met. Because the key to students' fruitful learning and comprehensive development lies here.

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